

**INCREASING THE ENGAGEMENT OF GRADE 3 LEARNERS
INTO READING THROUGH ULTIMATE PHONICS
READING PROGRAM**

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Increasing the Engagement of Grade 3 Learners into Reading Through Ultimate Phonics Reading Program

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Abstract

The COVID-19 pandemic has necessitated significant shifts in educational practices, with distance education emerging as a critical component for the forthcoming school year. This research proposal aims to evaluate the effectiveness of phonics reading materials in enhancing the reading engagement of Grade 3 learners at Cristo Rey West Elementary School. Utilizing an indirect questionnaire method, this research seeks to monitor and measure the reading frequency among students. The one-group pretest-posttest design will be employed, whereby a single group of students is assessed before and after exposure to the phonics program. The initial assessment will gauge current reading engagement levels, as reported by parents. Subsequently, a reading engagement survey, adapted from Whitaker (2003), will be administered to measure changes post-intervention. Data collection will coincide with the distribution and retrieval of learning modules, ensuring minimal disruption to the learners' routine. This study is pivotal in addressing the educational challenges posed by the pandemic, providing insights into the efficacy of targeted reading programs in a remote learning context. The findings will inform future strategies to enhance student engagement and literacy outcomes during unprecedented times.

Keywords: *engagement, reading, phonics, reading program*

Introduction

The pandemic that has engulfed the whole world has posted paradigm shift in all aspects of life's procedures and activities: one of these is our educational institutions from basic to higher education. Due to the health risks and protocols posted by concerned agencies, the reopening of classes for the forthcoming School Year may require assistance from parents as distance education may soon be inevitable. In fact, this will be the new normal of education in the coming months.

This research was organized ultimately to assist parents in their tasks of assisting, guiding, and teaching their children at home. The research center its competencies on building resilience at home amidst the pandemic enabling parents as academic tutors, learning the basics of using online platforms as the modality of the new normal, and building a culture of partnership, resourcefulness, and responsibility between parents and children.

Through the DepEd Order No. 012, s. 2020, Adoption of the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan for School Year 2020-2021 in the Light of the COVID-19 Public Health Emergency, In order to provide clear guidance to all offices, units, schools, and community learning centers (CLCs) of the Department of Education (DepEd), learners and their parents, partners, and stakeholders, the Department developed a Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP), a package of education interventions that will respond to basic education challenges brought about by COVID-19. In developing the BE-LCP, DepEd engaged internal and external stakeholders for inputs in the design of a learning delivery strategy and operational direction that ensures the health, safety, and well-being of all learners, teachers, and personnel of the Department.

The Philippines' dismal performance in reading, math and science in an assessment by an international agency is a wake up call for the country's educational system. Results of the Programme for International Learner Assessment (Pisa) by the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) showed that Filipino learners fared worst among 79 countries in reading comprehension and second-lowest in both mathematical and scientific literacy (Galvez, 2019).

Youths now days are not that well educated until they become effective readers. Since reading is the primary avenue to all knowledge, it offers access to inform, ideas, aspiration, and happenings of both future and the present. Furthermore, reading can invigorate individuals to be responsible productive members of the society. It is the vehicle of education, the means through which ideas, information, knowledge and wisdom are expressed and exchanged. Literate individuals possess the capacity to function fully in society: to make reasoned choices, to acquire meaningful employment, to participate in civic affairs.

Learning should never stop, right, and teachers should always find ways, even if they cannot meet face to face (Cortezano, 2020). Education must not stop, it's the basic right of an individual to be educated for the improvement of himself and the society he is in. Therefore, in this time of PANDEMIC, teachers and parents must adhere to the Deped's modalities on how to deliver the best education to the learners.

A Filipino child needs to develop higher order skills and functional literacy. It is given that any Filipino child with sufficient reading skills would have greater chances of success in school compared to a child whose reading skills are poor and more often than not, those with poor reading skills when assessed properly are diagnosed with reading disability. Poor reading skill is manifested with poor comprehension, wrong pronunciations, among others. If no proper intervention is administered early, it could affect the academic, social

and psychological development of the child. As such, proper and correct diagnosis of reading disability as early as possible appears to be essential (Cayubit, 2012).

Reading is a skill that is necessary to lead a successful life. One way to learn how to read is through the development of phonemic awareness. Learners are taught in small groups explicit phonics skills and this form of learning how to read can also be coupled with guided reading. This allows learners to be successful because instruction is directed at the learners reading ability, so the learners' learning is positively impacted (Powers, 2008).

Recognizing that there are still many Filipino learners that are struggling to meet the learning standards in early language, literacy, and numeracy, the Department of Education (DepEd) has “strongly encouraged” all elementary and secondary public schools to intensify their advocacy particularly for reading. In an effort to strengthen the reading proficiency of every learner and help nurture a culture of reading which considered a requisite skill in all content areas, DepEd announced the “Hamon: Bawa’t Bata Bumasa” (3Bs) initiative. Education Secretary Leonor Briones, in DepEd memorandum no. 173 s. of 2019, said that the 3Bs initiative will help strengthen the Every Child a Reader Program (ECRAP) which primarily aims to “equip learners with reading skills to make them proficient and independent readers in their grade level.” (Malipot, 2020).

Education Secretary Leonor M. Briones led in the launching of the Department of Education’s (DepEd) READ to LEAD Project (Reading Enhancement Approaches through Listening, Engaging And Doing) is part of the Sulong Edukalidad initiative of the DepEd which aims to enhance reading programs and approaches existing in schools, utilize assessment results in developing appropriate interventions that help improve the literacy skill of all types of learners, as well as upskill and reskill teachers in becoming effective reading instructors (Quitason, 2020).

Teaching children to read is a complicated process. Children begin school at varying levels of ability, yet are all required to meet a set standard of achievement. It is up to teachers to assess each learner, identify individual learning needs, and provide support. A motivating, literacy-rich program that includes whole-class, small-group, and individualized instruction is beneficial to struggling readers. Scripted and non-scripted literacy programs have proven to be effective, but it is the teacher who has the greatest effect on learner success (Kreitz, 2016).

Moving Readers from Struggling to Proficient, Wolter (2017) said that teachers must address the disparate ways that teachers respond to readers with varying abilities. Restorative practices, akin to restorative justice, build relationships, make connections, and foster a reader's sense of ownership and empowerment are necessary to help struggling readers take ownership for their reading growth and development.

Tracie (2018) noted that decoding deficits began in the early grades and without remediation created a subgroup of learners performing below the expected level of the grade level of achievement. Examining oral reading fluency and phonics instruction provided information to the effectiveness of these reading areas taught individually or in tandem using scripted programming, and what impacts the instruction had on narrowing the reading deficits. Without knowledge on what worked to remediate learners in reading, many school districts and teachers struggled with finding success.

The study of Tracie and the present study are similar because both studies aimed to determine how phonics instruction with the addition of a fluency program impacted learner reading growth. However, this study is unique because aside that the difficulties will be determined, a software will be use to help beginning and struggling readers of all ages to be accurate, fluent readers with higher comprehension.

Henry (2020) found that upper elementary readers who persist with reading difficulties face both academic and emotional challenges when they do not make reading gains equal to their peers. Decades of research has shown that persistent treatment resisters respond positively to a systematic multisensory phonics intervention. He examined how 5th and 6th grade struggling readers responded to a multisensory phonics intervention. Following the eight-week intervention, learners made gains in word reading accuracy and demonstrated increased confidence in word reading skills. Implications of the study bolster the importance of providing phonics instruction to older struggling readers.

The study of Henry is in consonance with the current study as they give the benefits and importance of setting an effective intervention in order to help learners who struggle in reading to overcome their reading difficulties and achieve reading success. Most learners who struggle with reading are missing essential fundamental skills. It is important to go back and establish the correct skills. On the other hand, they are different from each other because the former study used systematic multisensory phonics intervention while the present study utilized software license that can be use on all devices and a digital 600 manuals of organized reading material. Program uses colors, sound and more to engage learners of all ages.

Ultimate Phonics software helps parents teach beginning and struggling readers of all ages to be accurate, fluent readers with higher comprehension while learners learn at home. The Ultimate Phonics Reading Program turns the computer into a powerful teaching machine. It insures that children or learners learn the important phonics skills that are necessary for reading success. Whether it is used at home or in school, Ultimate Phonics provides a complete solution that enables parents and guardian to quickly, easily and completely ensure that their children and learners thoroughly learn those essential phonics skills.

The purpose of this study is to determine the reading performance of learners formatively assessed with Ultimate Phonics Reading Program compared with learners learning the traditional way. The researcher prompted to undertake this study to share ideas for how parents can support children at home in becoming an effective and confident reader and to solve serious reading problems such as word guessing or slow, laborious reading in this new normal of education.

Methodology

The researcher will utilize the indirect or questionnaire method in answering the questions in this study. This is in the form of the utilization of the developed and prepared phonics reading materials. According to Key (1997), the indirect method is most frequently a very concise, preplanned set of questions intended to generate specific information to address a particular need for research information about a pertinent topic. The indirect approach is needed for this research since it is important to monitor and measure the frequency of reading of the learners.

Research Design

The one-group pretest-posttest design will be used in this study. This design is implemented when a single group is pretested, exposed to a treatment, and then post tested. Due to the problems that everyone faces in the education sector during this pandemic, this design is fitted in this study since no control group will be required anymore.

An assessment will be administered to the Grade 3 learners of Cristo Rey West Elementary School. The reading engagement of these learners must have been low according to the reported observations of the parents at home. The measurement of the reading engagement of the learners will also be determined by adopting the reading engagement survey developed by SK Whitaker (2003). The distribution and retrieval of the test instruments will be done along with the distribution and retrieval of the learning modules. A re-assessment to the respondents will be conducted to test the increase in their reading engagement after the use of the proposed reading program.

Participants

The participants in this study will be the Grade 3 learners of Cristo Rey West Elementary School. The reading engagement of these learners must have been poor according to the reported observations of the parents at home.

Procedure

The researcher will prepare and improve phonics reading materials. An assessment will first be administered to determine who among the Grade 3 learners who are poorly engaged to reading. Based on the results of the assessment, phonics reading materials will be prepared. It will be validated by 3 experts after the initial preparation of the materials is completed. Their comments and appraisals will be recorded, and all their feedback will be considered in enhancing the materials. The improved materials will be used to the learners. An orientation to the learners will be done prior to the actual use.

A re-assessment will be administered to the previously identified poorly engaged to reading using the same reading engagement survey. The possible enhancement in their reading engagement will be tested by comparing the results before and after the utilization of the ultimate phonics reading program.

Ethical Considerations

For ethical considerations, the identity of the respondents will not be disclosed and their scores will not affect their academic ratings in this study. Consent forms from the parents of the respondents and assent forms to the respondents themselves will also be furnished. The procedures will also be explained thoroughly to the learners. Furthermore, no DepEd fund will be utilized in the gathering of data nor should any fee be collected from the respondents. The minimum health protocols proposed by the IATF will be strictly observed.

Results and Discussion

<i>Activities</i>	<i>Particular</i>	<i>Amount</i>
		Reproduction:
		60 pages x Php 5.00 x 5 copies = 1500.00
Reproduction of Approved Research	Approved Research	Php 75 book bind x 5 copies = 735.00
		Transportation:
		25.00 per hr x 1 hr = 25.00
	Sub-Total	1500+735+25=2260
	Grand Total	831.00 + 1461.00 + 2260.00 = 4552.00

The cost estimate in the conduct of this study will be Php 4452.00.

Plan for Dissemination and Advocacy

The results of this study are planned to be reported to the Division's LRMS, and the participants in this study. Copies are also planned to be furnished to the principal's office of Cristo Rey West Elementary School.

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